

SSC Whitepaper

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I. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The digitalization of the scientific process lead to the emergence of research software as a foundational pillar of modern research. However, the education and training that constitutes the academic profile of a scientist is domain-specific and does not in general cover aspects of software engineering best practices. This introduces two issues: (1) the lack of reproducibility and, in turn, lower credibility of the research output; (2) a barrier towards reaching excellence in research.

The Scientific Software Center (SSC) at Heidelberg University provides institutional support to researchers of all faculties of Heidelberg University in software development and software engineering best practices. The SSC promotes reproducibility and sustainability of research software, and provides services in research software development for researchers of all disciplines.

This whitepaper is intended to describe the SSC and its implementation strategy to aid in implementing research software engineering departments and institutional support at German universities and research institutions, as well as provide information to German funding agencies, policy makers and researchers at Heidelberg University.

FIG. 1. The three pillars of the SSC.

The support offered by the SSC is based on the three pillars **Development & Sustainability**, **Teaching & Consultation**, and **Outreach & Communication** (Fig. 1). The SSC's mission statement can be structured into these three areas; the overarching goal of the SSC's mission is to provide an infrastructure allowing access to customized research software, as well as access to fundamental and advanced software engineering training.

Mission Statement

The Scientific Software Center (SSC) strives to improve research software development practices at Heidelberg University and beyond, to promote reproducible science and research software sustainability.

Development & Sustainability:

- provide a research software infrastructure to support research
- provide development support for researchers who develop their own research software
- promote the use and re-use of research software
- foster synergies between scientific disciplines

Teaching & Consultation:

- provide training in software engineering for researchers who develop their own research software
- provide a low-barrier entry point for consultations about research software

Outreach & Communication:

- support and promote recognition of research software as scientific output, and research software engineering as viable academic career option
- promote and practice open-source access and sharing of research software

II. THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE SCIENTIFIC PROCESS: INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT

Digitalization is the cornerstone of modern research. While the scientific process itself remains largely unaffected, the way scientific research is carried out changed significantly in recent years[1]. The main emerging aspects are digital data and digital tools, where digital tools most often are research software. Both data and tools are closely interconnected; for one, the growing amount of data that is generated can only be analyzed using dedicated software. On the other hand, software can be used to generate synthetic data, for example to train a neural network, or to simulate the behaviour of complex systems based on theoretical approaches. Research software has become instrumental in carrying out cutting-edge research[2] and is the main focus at the Scientific Software Center (SSC). **Research software** is defined here as any computer program or application that is developed and used in the context of scientific research[3]. Research software is related to, but also different from application software: Application software serves a very specific purpose

with well-defined requirement specifications. Research or scientific software also serves specific purposes, but the exact requirements that need to be met are not well-defined in the beginning and have to be determined and refined iteratively through the scientific process[4, 5]. The skill set needed to develop research software encompasses both software engineering and scientific skills. Here, scientific skills do not necessarily correspond to domain expertise, but also more generally to the familiarity with the scientific process and approaches to solve scientific problems. These complimentary skill sets are what define a **Research Software Engineer** (RSE), a researcher who is familiar with both the scientific process and software engineering[6]. RSEs are largely responsible for developing and maintaining research software and play an essential role in the digital transformation of scientific research.

A majority of researchers report that software is critical for carrying out their research (70% in the 2014 software in research survey[7]). Half of these develop their own research software, where only half of the researchers that create scientific software have received training to do so. Inevitably, the lack of skills introduces errors, resulting in a failure to adhere to scientific best practices and to obtain reproducible scientific results[8]. This in turn leads to paper retractions at best[9, 10], but unfortunately can also have more severe consequences[9, 11]. In the OECD International Survey of Scientific Authors[12], researchers state that the biggest challenges to their research are the lack of skills (25%), lack of digital infrastructure and tools (35%), and missing access to data (35%). The most important infrastructure named in the survey is internet access, directly followed by software. The survey participants rank advanced programming skills as the third most important skill after project management (first) and data collection/curation (second).

As a result, the need for an infrastructure providing access to customized research software, as well as access to fundamental and advanced software engineering training have been identified[1, 2, 13–15], among others. These two main aspects are at the focus of the SSC, and are formulated in the SSC’s mission statement. As such, the SSC provides key services to researchers at Heidelberg University in a *centralized* as well as a *decentralized* manner. Centralized support is available through the SSC’s own RSEs; decentralized support through fostering autonomy and self-reliance, by providing consultation and training. In the latter case, the research groups themselves employ RSEs among their staff. The optimal type of support depends on the scientific domain, the research question, the composition of the research group, and other factors, and is determined on a case-by-case basis. The SSC’s offers are open to all researchers of Heidelberg University, irrespective of their scientific domain or career status. The first step towards getting support is through a consultation (see section IV).

A major obstacle to ensuring sustainability of research software is the lack of funding for software maintenance[2, 13, 15], unfortunately this aspect cannot be covered by the SSC at this point.

III. DEVELOPMENT & SUSTAINABILITY

Aim

- Support researchers with high-quality, sustainable research software that generates reproducible data
- Provide access to well-trained RSEs
- Provide a career option and a community to RSEs
- Adapt the latest software engineering standards in the development of research software

A. Strategy

The support in the D&S pillar spans from a **small-scale project** over an **open call project** to a **third-party funded project**. The starting point for any development support through the

<i>type of support</i>	small-scale project	open call project	third-party funded project
<i>time scale</i>	1 week	1 – 12 months	> 1 month
<i>cost</i>	free of charge	free of charge	determined in consultation
<i>availability</i>	throughout the year	proposal submission deadline mid-June	throughout the year depending on availability of resources

SSC is always a consultation (see next section). Here, the most suitable support mode as well as the feasibility of the planned project is determined. A consultation can develop into a small-scale project; this means that the SSC will provide approximately one week of workforce solving the task defined in the consultation. Larger projects are candidates for the annual open call or for a proposal for external funding. Often, projects follow a progression from small-scale to open call/third-party funded projects.

Small-scale project: Small-scale projects are carried out throughout the year upon availability of resources and are selected through a consultation. In a small-scale project, the SSC supports

the researchers with one week of development time. This type of project can serve to create a software prototype, a new feature, increase the efficiency of existing research software, or provide a starting point for implementing best practices in existing research software.

Open call project: Open call projects are selected from proposals submitted to the SSC’s open call. The open call is usually announced in April each year and closes in June. Open call projects provide access to the SSC’s workforce for one to twelve months of developer time and offer substantial support for a scientist’s research project. Open call projects can be used to create new research software or features, increase the efficiency of existing research software, or implement best practices in existing research software, as well as improve the code-base of existing research software. They are free of charge.

Third-party funded project: In a third-party funded project, the SSC can be involved in the grant application and proposal writing from the beginning and act as a partner (either as co-applicant or as a service partner). The SSC can also provide support to ongoing research projects on a paid basis (previously obtained funds of the researchers are used as a “buy-in” to access RSE developer time; corresponding to an RSE of the SSC temporarily joining a research group). Third-party funded projects are mostly about implementing new features or creating a new piece of research software. This is mainly due to the nature of calls for funding - there are a few exceptions that allow other types of support, for example refactoring and increasing the usability of a research software[16]. The type of involvement of the SSC, the feasibility of the support, availability of resources and related service cost is determined in an initial consultation.

Examples for all types of support are given in the Appendix VII A.

IV. TEACHING & CONSULTATION

Aim

- Provide training in software engineering best practices
- Spread the use of best practices in the community
- Provide an easy, low-barrier entrance point for researchers, directly provide feedback on software quality or software-related questions

A. Strategy

The training in the pillar T&C targets individuals with experience in the scientific process who are involved in research projects. These are usually PhD students and Postdocs. Most SSC courses are offered as half-day or one-day **compact courses**. The topics covered in the courses are repeated on a regular basis. Further, **on-demand courses** can also be booked; these are scheduled once a sufficient number of subscribers has been reached. In addition to these, the SSC also offers **block courses** (several days) and **seminars** (on a recurring basis). To advertise the courses and encourage student participation, the SSC works closely together with the graduate schools at Heidelberg University. The graduate students can get credit points for a successful participation, that count towards their required total. Students from 4EU+ universities¹ can also take part in the courses.

The courses are meant to complement the existing curricula and cover topics from version control over performance engineering to programming language-specific topics. Programming languages per se are not covered by the SSC, these are subject of standard lectures. Ideas for new courses can be suggested anytime; meanwhile the SSC also develops new courses based on requests and importance in the field.

The SSC also offers a **mentoring program** “SSC fellows” to PhD students and Postdocs at Heidelberg University. Additionally, student assistants have the opportunity to work with the SSC on all types of projects, thus learning about exciting new research in various fields and the connection to the technical domain. These student assistants receive training in software engineering by the SSC to consolidate their profile and help the students advance to the next career level. Research groups at Heidelberg University profit from this as their prospective Master/PhD students will have acquired valuable technical skills.

In addition to training through courses, **consultations** provide one-to-one access to the SSC’s RSEs. Consultations can be scheduled anytime. The basis of a consultation is formed for example by the scientist’s research question, the input and output data, the involved research software, to name a few. Ideally, these details are already provided before the consultation. The purpose of a consultation is manifold. One aspect is education about best practices, but even more importantly **a consultation is the basis for any development project of the SSC**. A consultation is always the first step to gain access to the SSC’s specifically trained RSEs.

Consultations and training are free and open at all times to Heidelberg University’s researchers

¹ <https://4euplus.eu/4EU-1.html>

of all faculties and at all career stages, independent of the software affinity of their research.

In addition, the SSC also offers online material such as Software Engineering Guidelines and Template Repositories on GitHub. All course material is licensed under a free license and available online.

Examples for courses offered by the SSC are given in the Appendix VII B.

V. OUTREACH & COMMUNICATION

Aim

- Improve recognition of research software as scientific output, and support and shape RSE career paths
- Develop and maintain official guidelines and policies for research software development
- Actively participate in national and international software engineering initiatives and communities
- Contribute to open-source software and open science

A. Strategy

The SSC actively participates in community calls such as the joint monthly call of de-RSE, Open Science AG and GRN/Carpentries. Further, SSC members participate and present at RSE meetings and Open Science conferences. The software developed by the SSC, and the software the SSC contributes to, is published with an open-source license if possible and accompanied by a publication that describes the software, making the software citable.

The SSC provides an inclusive workspace to RSEs, with the RSEs working on projects depending on their interest and background, enabling life-long learning and fostering a culture of continuous skill development. Further, an umbrella for RSEs working in research groups at Heidelberg University is built up that provides identity. This is achieved by regular open meet-ups where all RSEs of Heidelberg University are welcome to interact and share experiences. The SSC also supports its RSEs in strengthening their academic profile and aiding them in identifying suitable follow-up positions.

The SSC is contact point for the development of guidelines and policies i.e. in research software management and licensing, and works together with local institutions such as the Research Data

Unit² toward reproducible and open science.

As an institution that provides training, the SSC recognizes and connects with national and international initiatives such as SURESOFT³ and the Carpentries.

Examples for SSC activities in the O&C pillar are found in the Appendix VII C.

VI. ACHIEVEMENTS

So far, the SSC has completed two rounds of open call projects (currently in the third cycle), and a multitude of small-scale projects and consultations. The demand for third-party funded projects is continuously rising and has enabled a growth from an initial team of three RSEs in fall 2020 to seven RSEs in spring 2024. A summary of growth quantifiers is given in Table I.

TABLE I. Growth quantifiers over the three years of the SSC activities and estimate into 2024.

<i>type of quantifier</i>	2021	2022	2023	2024
<i>RSE / FTE^a</i>	3.0	3.5	5.5	7.0
<i>oversubscription to open call / %</i>	140	300	300	tbd
<i>third-party funding / % SSC core budget</i>	0	2	32	>47

^a full-time equivalent

A visualization of topic areas of the previous and current small-scale and open call projects is found in Fig. 2, highlighting that the SSC has supported researchers from a wide range of fields.

The courses offered by the SSC have received widespread interest, approval, and very positive feedback of the participants. Participants of the courses come from all career stages: Master students, PhD students, Postdoctoral researchers and also group leaders.

VII. APPENDIX

A. Development & Sustainability: Examples

Below is a list of a few examples for the different types of projects carried out by the SSC.

Small-scale project: A researcher asked for support with the efficiency of their in-house code.

The Python script written by the researchers was of limited performance and prohibited an analysis of large amounts of data in a timely manner⁴. The SSC replaced the bottleneck

² <https://www.data.uni-heidelberg.de/>

³ <https://suresoft.dev/>

⁴ <https://www.ssc.uni-heidelberg.de/en/development/all-projects/hamming-distance>

FIG. 2. Subject areas covered by SSC projects, relative numbers per project type.

procedures with a highly optimized, vectorized and parallelized C++ version. This library was packaged as the Python library `hammingdist` to fit into the existing analysis pipeline. The code now runs several orders of magnitude faster, and scales using HPC resources to process hundreds of thousands of gene expressions[17, 18].

Another researcher asked for support in extracting text from social media images. The images were taken as screenshots from a Wayback Machine archive, as the original websites and posts do not exist anymore. The text on the images was in multiple languages, and the images were often blurry. The researcher tried to find a way to automatize the text extraction, as there were several hundred images, but failed to produce accurate results due to the low quality of the images. The SSC tested different open-source libraries for this task and generated a first prototype to aid in the research project. This project evolved into the open call project “Misinformation campaign characteristics”⁵ or “ammico” (AI Media and Misinformation Content Analysis)⁶[19, 20]. Here, the SSC developed a software package to automatically extract text from social media posts and images, and translate and analyse the text; as well as analyse the image content through image captioning, visual question answering, multimodal analysis and color analysis. The software package has already found re-use in other researcher’s projects.

⁵ <https://www.ssc.uni-heidelberg.de/en/development/all-projects/misinformation-campaigns-characteristics>

⁶ <https://github.com/ssciwr/AMMICO>

Open call project: The project “Visuomotor serial targeting task” (VSTT)⁷ supported researchers in the Institute of Sports and Sports Science: a software was developed that allows to carry out various motor learning paradigms. The package VSTT⁸ is an open source GUI tool for designing, running and analyzing motor skill acquisition experiments. It allows researchers to quickly and easily construct a wide range of visuomotor task experiments, run these experiments and analyse the results. The software is easy to install and use. It supports Windows, Mac and Linux operating systems.

In the project “Change detection in 4D point cloud data” (p4dgeo), the SSC provided a unified implementation of different automatic geographic analysis methods of 3D point clouds captured over time with LiDAR or photogrammetry. Such (3D space + time) point clouds are omnipresent in geosciences, environmental, ecological and archaeological sciences, robotics, and many more fields and applications. Performance-critical algorithms were implemented using C++, the resulting package p4dgeo⁹ provides access to the library through Python bindings.

Third-party funded project: The project SampleFlow¹⁰ allows multiplexed nanopore DNA sequencing as a trial service to other groups within Heidelberg University. A web service was set up for users to submit samples and to automatically receive their results. Users can sign up for an account, log in, upload sequences, request samples, and download their results. The server automatically emails users with their results when they are submitted by the lab analysis script. The tech stack used involves a vue.js frontend, flask backend, REST API, JWT authentication, and docker.

Spatial Model Editor¹¹ provides a user friendly GUI editor to create and edit spatial SBML (Systems Biology Markup Language) models of bio-chemical reactions and simulate them using the dune-copasi solver[?] for reaction-diffusion systems. The goal of this project is to extend the software from two-dimensional to three-dimensional spatial models, which involves multiple aspects including image segmentation, meshing, PDEs (Partial Differential Equations) and SBML.

In the project “Fostering a community-driven and sustainable HELIOS++ scientific software”, HELIOS++[21] is refactored and developed into a general-purpose integrated platform for users and developers from a broad spectrum of scientific disciplines. HELIOS++,

⁷ <https://www.ssc.uni-heidelberg.de/en/development/all-projects/visuomotor-serial-targeting-task-vstt>

⁸ <https://vstt.readthedocs.io>

⁹ <https://github.com/3dgeo-heidelberg/py4dgeo>

¹⁰ <https://circuitseq.iwr.uni-heidelberg.de/>

¹¹ <https://spatial-model-editor.readthedocs.io>

the “Heidelberg LiDAR Operations Simulator”, is used to mimic real topographic laser scanning in a computer environment (virtual laser scanning (VLS)).

In the project “Establishing a knowledge graph community in biomedical science”, OmniPath[22] and related software will be restructured to make it more usable, scalable and extensible. OmniPath integrates over 100 different resources focused on molecular knowledge, for example about genes, proteins, and diseases.

The last two projects are funded through the DFG program ”Research Software - Quality Assured and Re-usable: Call for Proposals to Increase the Usability of Existing Research Software”[16].

B. Teaching & Consultation: Examples

Below is a list of a few examples of different courses offered by the SSC.

Compact courses: The SSC offers a two-part compact course on the Unix shell (part 1) and version control with `git` (part 2). This course is typically repeated every semester. The first part covers how and why to use the Unix shell, handling files and directories using the command line, advanced usage of the shell like loops, pipes, redirects and how to write workflows as reusable shell scripts. In the second part, the benefits of using version control are explained, the basic `git` terminology and common tasks in `git`. Participants learn how `git` repositories can help them to move towards practicing Open Science. The course material was adapted from the Software Carpentries’ portfolio and is taught by a certified Software Carpentry instructor.

Another half-day course covers performance benchmarking C++ applications. Participants learn how to integrate microbenchmarks into their C++ codebase, and how to measure performance using sampling tools like `perf` and simulation tools like `callgrind`.

Another half-day course covers Python Best Practices and is specific to the Python programming language. Participants learn to understand and use the basic naming conventions in Python, how to use a linter and code formatter, how to write better and more readable code, and about common pitfalls in Python.

Block courses: A block course offered by the SSC is “Scientific Software Development”¹², that runs over the course of a week (half days). This course covers the life cycle of scientific software, from an initial Jupyter notebook to publishing a Python package. Participants

¹² https://ssciwr.github.io/sustainable_development_course/

learn to use the `git` version-control system and collaborate in teams through GitHub, use an integrated development environment, use a linter and code formatter, understand the best practices for planning a piece of software, write `Pytest` unit tests, use `Sphinx` to build a documentation, ensure reproducibility through automated testing with GitHub actions, and understand the basics of publishing a Python package.

Seminar: The recurring seminar series “Lunch time python” introduces Python libraries through a 30-minute online format. All material is made available online¹³ and can be explored interactively on google colab or Binder.

C. Outreach & Communication: Examples

Below is a list of a few examples of the SSC’s activities in the O&C pillar.

Participation in conferences: The SSC participates and presents in national and international RSE and Open Science meetings. The contributions range over a large variety of topics, from library-specific talks to general talks and workshops about the role of research software and research software engineering in open science.

de-RSE position paper: The SSC leads a current initiative of the de-RSE e.V. in writing a position paper about establishing Research Software Engineering infrastructures at German research institutions. In this community-driven process, the requirements and targets for infrastructures such as the SSC are defined, to serve as a guideline for universities and research institutions.

Research Software Directory: The SSC supports the visibility of research software by establishing a ‘Research Software Directory.’ In this database, software packages developed by researchers at the University of Heidelberg are listed. The Research Software Directory serves to encourage networking and to further the recognition of research software as a scientific achievement.

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¹³ <https://github.com/ssciwr/lunch-time-python>

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